

A SURVEY OF THE MANTIDEA FAMILY IN DIFFERENT AREAS OF IRAQ

Rashid Ismail Taha, Prof. Dr. Ahmed Ali Issa

Department of Biology, College of sciences, University of Tikrit-Iraq

Prof. Dr. Haider Badri Ali

Department of Biology, College of sciences, University of Baghdad –Iraq

Abstract: The current study included a taxonomic and phenotypic study of the Mantidae family in different regions of Iraq (Baghdad, Salah al-Din, Kirkuk) for the period from April 1, 2023 to March 6, 2024, and during this study 3 species belonging to 3 genera were described.

Through this study, the head, thoracic and abdominal regions and some body appendages of each species were studied, and the phenotypic differences between males and females in the same species and between the different species studied were observed as follows:

1- Genus: *Mantis religiosa* Linnaeus, 1758

This species was recorded in Baghdad, Salah al-Din, Kirkuk, during the month of April 1, 2023 to March 6, 2024, and some preserved samples were obtained at the Natural History Research Center and Museum / University Baghdad, which were collected from Nineveh Governorate in 1963, and some preserved samples were obtained in the University of Baghdad Museum / College of Science / Department of Life Sciences.

2- Genus: *Empusa hedenorgii* Stal, 1877

This species was recorded in Salah al-Din, Kirkuk, Baghdad, during the month of April 1, 2023 to March 6, 2024, in addition to studying the samples present in the Natural History Research Center and Museum / University of Baghdad, which were collected from Nineveh Governorate in 1963, as well as the unidentified samples in the University of Baghdad / College of Science / Department of Life Sciences.

3- Genus: *Blepharopsis mendica* (Fabricius 1775)

This species was recorded during the study period in Kirkuk, Baghdad, Erbil from May, June and July 2022, and some existing and identified samples were studied in the Natural History Research Center and Museum / University of Baghdad, which were collected from Nineveh Governorate in 1963.

Keyword: *Mantidea Mantis religiosa, Empusa hedenorgii, Blepharopsis mendica.*

Introduction:

Insects of the order Mantodea are divided into 25 families worldwide. The praying mantis family Mantidae belongs to the order Mantodea [1], this family was divided into four subfamilies and included the following: Subfamily1: Amelinae, Subfamily2: Miomantinae, Subfamily3: Mantinae, Subfamily4: Oxyothespinae, Subfamily5 Mimomantinae [2].

Insects belonging to the Mantidae family are of great economic importance as they are considered predatory insects that eliminate many other insects that are harmful to field crops and include more than 2400 species [3,4] The family is distributed worldwide and contains approximately 2,300 species of mantises distributed in 434 genera[5].

Praying mantises are highly effective predators that capture and eat a variety of insects and other small prey. They are excellent pesticides, reducing the numbers of various insects that pose a threat to agriculture, and thus can be used as an effective biological control agent. They are one of the most important insects in every ecosystem. They usually prey on other insects, but they sometimes attack small vertebrates such as snakes, lizards, frogs, and hummingbirds[6].

The praying mantis got its common name from the way it raises its front legs in a prayer position. The insect often waits for hours without moving to obtain its prey, with its head rotating 180 degrees. It is a diurnal insect that sits on grasses, shrubs and trees and is also attracted to lights at night to feed]7,8,9[.

Praying mantises play an important role in controlling the ecosystem. They help control the terrestrial ecosystem as well as other ecosystems]10[.

The praying mantis Mantodea plays an important role in controlling enemies and harmful insect pests. It feeds on a variety of other insects such as grasshoppers, moths, flies, aphids and other insects]11,12[.

Materials and Methods

Survey and Sample Collection

We conducted multiple trips to many districts, sub-districts and villages that were adjacent to the river (Tigris, Zab) and which are characterized by their agricultural environment of field crops, orchards and various farms, affiliated with the governorates (Baghdad, Salah al-Din, Kirkuk) for the period from April 1/4/2023 to March 6/3/2024 at intermittent periods and according to the available capabilities.

Sample Collection

Various field trips were conducted, as the sweeping net was used to collect samples located between plants and the aerial net to collect flying samples, as sample collection begins from the beginning of the agricultural field randomly by observing the presence of the insect on the plants or its flight in the field.

After that, the contents of the net are emptied from the samples into plastic containers of different sizes 60-100 ml tightly closed, and information about the place of collection and date is recorded on each plastic container.

During the research period, 110 samples of different species of the Mantidae family were collected.

Sample examination

The samples were examined visually using different dissecting microscopes (Amscoe Dissecting Microscope, NOVEL Dissecting Microscope) as these microscopes differ in their design and magnification power. The complete samples and their different parts were photographed using the Camera Microscope Amscoe FM050. A Samsung Galaxy A70, iPhone 14 mobile phone was also used to photograph the insect and all its parts. The complete insect and all parts were measured using a regular ruler.

Sample Diagnosis

The diagnostic keys of the Mantidae family were adopted to isolate and diagnose the genera and species of a number of researchers]13[. Some samples were also compared with the species previously preserved and diagnosed at the Natural History Research Center and Museum / University of Baghdad.

Dissection and study of the external appearance

The parts of the complete insect were studied by placing them in a 100 ml glass beaker in which a small amount of water was placed to half, then it was placed on a heat source (heater) until the water vapor rose, after which the insect was fixed on a piece of cork and placed inside this beaker and monitored until the insect's body was completely softened by water vapor, after which all the different parts of the insect's body were separated (the fin, antennae, wings, thorax, leg, abdomen), taking into account the several breakages of these parts.

Several types of pins of different sizes were used for fixation and large and small forceps were used to separate all parts from each other.

Then the head, chest and abdomen were transferred to another 100 ml beaker containing 10% KOH solution and left for (2-3) hours to easily disassemble the muscles and also to get rid of the fat inside these parts.

Then the separated parts were transferred to a petri dish and washed with distilled water several times to remove the KOH and then transferred to a clean watch bottle containing distilled water to separate the different mouth parts of the head, the dorsal plate and the sternal plates of the abdominal region.

Results

Through the study, the following results were obtained

	Measurements	<i>Empusa hedenborgii</i>		<i>Blepharopsis mendica</i>		<i>Mantis religiosa</i>	
		males	Males	Males	Males	males	Males
1	Body length	5.7 – 6.1	5.8 – 6.6	4.7 – 4.8	4.8 – 5	5.3-5.5	5.4-5.5
2	Head width	0.3 – 0.5	0.4 – 0.6	0.7 – 0.8	0.7 – 1	0.5-0.8	0.6-0.7
3	Pronotum length	2.2 – 2.5	2.2 - 2.8	1.2 – 1.5	1.4 – 1.8	1.5-1.7	1.8-2
4	Metazone length	1.8 – 2.2	2 – 2.6	0.8 – 1	0.8 – 1.1	1.1-1.2	1.2-1.5
5	Maximum pronotum width	0.32 – 0.5	0.4 – 0.6	0.3 – 0.4	0.3 – 0.4	0.4-0.6	0.5-0.8
6	Minimum pronotum width	0.2 – 0.4	0.3 - 0.48	0.3 – 0.4	0.3 – 0.5	0.3-0.4	0.4-0.6
7	Length of fore coxa	1.1 – 1.6	1.3 – 1.8	1.2 – 1.5	1.5 – 1.6	1.0-1.2	1.2-1.5
8	Length of fore femur	1.5 – 1.7	1.5 – 1.9	1.5 – 1.7	1.6 – 1.9	1.4-1.5	1.6-1.8
9	Length of fore tibia	0.7 – 0.9	1.8 – 2	0.9 – 1	1.1 – 1.3	0.6-0.7	0.8-1
10	Length of hind femur	1.5 – 1.7	1.8 – 2	1.6 – 1.8	1.7 – 2	1.5-1.6	1.7-1.9
11	Length of hind tibia	1.55 – 1.66	1.7 – 1.9	1.5 – 1.7	1.5 -1.8	1.5-1.6	1.6-1.8
12	Length of elytra	3 – 3.3	3.2 – 3.5	4.1 – 4.6	4.5 – 4.8	3.7-3.9	4.5- 4.8
13	Maximum elytron width distal of jugal	0.6 – 0.8	0.6 – 1	1.1 – 1.22	1.1 – 1.5	0.88-0.9	0.9-1

Conclusions:

1. During this study, 3 species belonging to three genera were recorded.
2. The most widespread species is *Mantis religiosa* Linnaeus, 1758, as it was collected from most of the governorates included in the study.
3. These species are spread in agricultural environments with high plant density, which helps them in hiding and feeding.
4. The characteristics of the external appearance, especially the thorns spread in the first pair of legs, can be relied upon in designing the key to isolate the species and genera.
5. Mantis insects are considered to be of economic importance, through their feeding on many other insects that harm agricultural crops.

Photo (1A) Dorsal view of a female of the species *Mantis religiosa* Photo (1B) Anterior view of the forelegs of the species *Mantis religiosa*

Image (2A) Abdominal region of a female *Mantis religiosa* Image (2B) Abdominal region of a male *Mantis religiosa*

(2C) Male genitalia of the species *Mantis religiosa*

Photo (3A) Dorsal view of *Empusa hedenborgii* Photo (3B) Lateral view of *Empusa hedenborgii* Photo (3C) Forelegs of *Empusa hedenborgii*

Photo (4 A) The abdominal region of a female *Empusa hedenborgii* Photo (4 B) The abdominal region of a male *Empusa hedenborgii* Photo (4 C) The male genitalia of the species *Empusa hedenborgii*

Figure (5 A) Dorsal view of the species *Blepharopsis mendica* Figure (5 B) Head and thorax of *Blepharopsis mendica* Figure (5 C) Male genitalia of *Blepharopsis mendica*

Figure (6A) The abdominal region of a female *Blepharopsis mendica* Figure (6B) The abdominal region of a male *Blepharopsis mendica* Figure (6C) The forelegs of the species *Blepharopsis mendica*

Referenc

1. Otte, Daniel, Lauren Spearman and Martin B.D. Stiewe. 2020. *Mantodea Species File Online*. Version 5.0/5.0. (06.04.2020). <http://Mantodea.SpeciesFile.org>.
2. Mirzaee, Z., Sadeghi, S. (2019). On a summer collection of mantids (Insecta: Mantodea) from Lorestan province with nine new records. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics (IJAB)*. 15(2), pp.1-13. DOI: 10.22067/ijab.v15i2.79314
3. Svenson, G.J. & Whiting, M.F. 2009. Reconstructing the origins of praying mantises (Dictyoptera, Mantodea): The roles of Gondwanan vicariance and morphological convergence. – *Cladistics* 25(5): 468-514.

4. Klass, K.-D. & Ehrmann, R. 2003. 13. Ordnung Mantodea, Fangschrecken, Gottesanbeterinnen. – Pp. 182-197 in: Dathe, H.H. (ed.): Lehrbuch der Speziellen Zoologie, Band I: Wirbellose Tiere, 5. Teil: Insecta. – Heidelberg, Berlin: Spektrum. 961 pp. DOI:10.1111/j.1096-0031.2009.00263.x
5. Wieland, F., Svenson, G. J. (2018) Biodiversity of Mantodea. Pp. 389–416. In: R. G. Foottit, P. H. Adler (Eds.). *Insect biodiversity: science and society Volume II*. John Wiley & Sons Ltd, Oxford, United Kingdom. DOI: 10.1002/9781118945582.ch15
6. Battiston, R., and P. Fontana. 2010. “Colour Change and Habitat Preferences in Mantis *Religiosa* (Insecta Mantodea).” *Bulletin of Insectology* 63 (1): 85–89.
7. Sureshan, P.M. & Sambath, S. 2009. Mantid (Insecta: Mantodea) fauna of old Bihar (Bihar and Jharkhand) with some new records for the state. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India*, 109(3): 11–26. <https://doi.org/10.26515/rzsi/v109/i3/2009/158988>
8. Dutta W, Sur D. Praying Mantis: A threatened group of insect from Purulia, West Bengal. *Biodiversity Conservation: Fundamentals and Applications*, 2012, 262-263. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.1.3579.2722
9. Sathe TV, Vaishali PJ. Report on nine new species of mantids (Insecta: Mantodea) and their insect pest predatory potential from agroecosystems of Kolhapur region, *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*. 2014; 2(5):304-307. DOI:10.13140/2.1.4212.1926
10. Pashaie Rad, S. and Mirzaee, Z. , (2018). Seven new records of Mantids (Insecta: Mantodea) for Alborz Mountain, (Tehran Province) Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics*, 13(2). 221-228. DOI:10.22067/ijab.v13i2.61900
11. Uvarov B.P., dirsh V.M., 1952. Orthoptera collected in Iran. *Ergebnisse einer botanischzoologischen Sammelreise durch den Iran 1948/49. Verhandlungen der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Basel*; 63, 1-16.
12. Uvarov. , 1938. Orthoptera from Iraq and Iran. *Zoology Ser. Field. Museum Natural History*; 20, 439-451. <http://pi.lib.uchicago.edu/1001/cat/bib/4094170>
13. Ghahari., M.G. EL-Den Nasser., 2014. A contribution to the knowledge of Mantodea (Insecta) fauna of Iran. *Linzer biologische Beitrage*; 46, 665-673.
14. Khairallah, B. A., Muhammad, F. M., Saleh, J. N., & Saleh, M. J. (2024). Preparation, Characterization, Biological Activity Evaluation, and Liquid Crystallography Study of New Diazepine Derivatives. *World of Medicine: Journal of Biomedical Sciences*, 1(7), 65-76.
15. Mohammed Jwher Saleh, Jamil Nadhem Saleh, Khalid Al-Badrany, Adil Hussein Dalaf, Reem Suhail Najm, & Abdul Wahed Abdul Sattar Talluh. (2024). Preparation And Evaluation Of The Biological Activity Of A 2- Amino Pyran Ring Using A Solid Base Catalyst. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4), 130 - 138.
16. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). Preparation, Characterisation and Study of the Molecular Docking of Some Derivatives of the Tetrazole Ring and Evaluation of their Biological Activity. *World of Medicine: Journal of Biomedical Sciences*, 1(7), 15-23.
17. Dalaf, A. H., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). GREEN SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION, AND MULTIFACETED EVALUATION OF THIAZOLIDINONE DERIVATIVES: A STUDY ON BIOLOGICAL AND LASER EFFICACY. *European Journal of Modern Medicine and Practice*, 4(7), 155-168.
18. Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., & Al-Badrany, K. (2024). PREPARATION, CHARACTERIZATION, AND EVALUATION OF THE BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF PYRAZOLINE DERIVATIVES PREPARED

- USING A SOLID BASE CATALYST. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(7), 25-32.
19. Saleh, J. N., & Khalid, A. (2023). Synthesis, characterization and biological activity evaluation of some new pyrimidine derivatives by solid base catalyst AL₂O₃-OBa. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(4), 231-239.
 20. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, J. N., & Saleh, M. J. (2024). Preparation, Characterization and Evaluation of Biological Activity and Study of Molecular Docking of Some New Thiazoli-dine Derivatives.
 21. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., Al-Badrany, K., & mohammed saleh Al-Jubori, H. (2024). Preparation, characterization, and evaluation of the biological activity of new 2, 3-dihydroquinazoline-4-one derivatives. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 326-332.
 22. Talluh, A. W. A. S. (2024). Preparation, Characterization, Evaluation of Biological Activity, and Study of Molecular Docking of Azetidine Derivatives. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(1), 608-616.
 23. Saleh, M. J., & Al-Badrany, K. A. (2023). Preparation, characterization of new 2-oxo pyran derivatives by AL₂O₃-OK solid base catalyst and biological activity evaluation. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(4), 222-230.
 24. Muhammad, F. M., Khairallah, B. A., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh, J. N. (2024). Preparation and Characterization of New Rings of Oxazine Derivatives and Studying Their Biological and Laser Effectiveness and Molecular Docking. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 5(4), 190-201.
 25. Sattar Talluh, A. W. A., Saleh, J. N., Saleh, M. J., & Saleh Al-Jubori, H. M. (2024). Preparation and Characterization of New Imidazole Derivatives Derived From Hydrazones and Study of their Biological and Laser Efficacy. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 5(4), 202-211.
 26. Saleh, M. M., Saleh, J. N., Rokan, F. F., & Saleh, M. J. (2024). Synthesis, Characterization and evaluation of bacterial efficacy and study of molecular substrates of cobalt (II) complex [Co (2-(benzo [d] thiazol-2-yloxy) acetohydrazide)(H₂O)(Cl₂)]. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4).
 27. Talluh, A. W. A. S., Saleh, M. J., Saleh, J. N., & Al-Jubori, H. M. S. (2024). Synthesis and Characterization of Some New Imine Graphene Derivatives and Evaluation of Their Biological Activity. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 5(4), 272-290.
 28. Abdul Wahed, A. S. T. (2024). Preparation and Evaluation of Bacterial Activity and Study of the Crystalline Properties of Some 1, 3-Oxazepine-4, 7-Dione Derivatives. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 5(2), 15-26.